

Serpulid Morphogroups (M.ID) of the Otago harbour, New Zealand

Winter season + a small subset of Spring 2021

Tom Massué

University of Otago, Department of Marine Science

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm):
- Coiling direction: [Sinistral / Dextral / longitudinal]
- Shell shape: [Planispiral / Conispiral]
- External ornaments: [keels + peristomes]

- Texture of the tube: [Opaque / translucent]

- Teeth:

- Colour:

Frequency on Panels

Common Less common Rare

[Subfamily]
[M.ID]

[M.ID tube features
+
[illustration]

[M.ID illustrations]

[M.ID illustrations]

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 3.0
- Coiling direction: *Sinistral*
- Shell shape: *Conispiral sometimes helically*
- External ornaments: *Lateral "fluffy" longitudinal keel, growth lines.*
- Texture of the tube: *Translucent aspect, smooth.*
- Teeth: *None.*
- Colour: *Grey/pink*

Frequency on Panels

Common Less common Rare

Spirorbinae

M.ID 1

S.C.19

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 3.0
- Coiling direction: *Sinistral*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *Lateral "teeth shape" longitudinal keel, 2 elevated keels strongly segmented.*
- Texture of the tube: *Alveoli between keels, rough.*
- Teeth: *None to one.*
- Colour: *Brownish, pinkish.*

Frequency on Panels

Common Less common Rare

Spirorbinae

M.ID 2

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 2.0 to 3.5
- Coiling direction: *Sinistral*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *Lateral large, flat, smooth longitudinal keel.*
- Texture of the tube: *Opaque, smooth and compact.*
- Teeth: *One large middle.*
- Colour: *White*

Serpulinae

M.ID 3

Frequency on Panels		
Common	Less common	Rare

W.C.43

W.C.48

W.C.9

W.C.37

W.D.14

W.D.16

W.D.17

W.D.23

W.1.3

W.2.29

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 1.0
- Coiling direction: *Sinistral*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *None obvious.*
- Texture of the tube: Smooth and opaque.
- Teeth: *None.*
- Colour: *White*

Spirorbinae

M.ID 4

Frequency on Panels

Common **Less common** Rare

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 2.0
- Coiling direction: *Sinistral*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *3 longitudinal keels, segmentation between keels.*
- Texture of the tube: *Smooth and opaque.*
- Teeth: *3 teeth*
- Colour: *White*

Frequency on Panels

Common **Less common** Rare

Spirorbinae

M.ID 5

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 3.0
- Coiling direction: *Dextral*
- Shell shape: *Conispiral*
- External ornaments: *3 thick longitudinal keels, thick peristomes.*
- Texture of the tube: *Large and thick aperture, alveoli between keels, rough.*
- Teeth: *None.*
- Colour: *White*

Frequency on Panels

Common Less common Rare

Spirorbinae

M.ID 6

Late settle stage M.ID 6

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 1.0
- Coiling direction: *Dextral*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *Thick double median longitudinal keels, one lateral keel.*
- Texture of the tube: *Opaque, smooth, and compact.*
- Teeth: *1 large.*
- Colour: *White.*

Frequency on Panels

Common

Less common

Rare

Spirorbinae

M.ID 7

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): ~ 2.5
- Coiling direction: *Dextral*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *3 thick, rounded, and elevated longitudinal keels.*
- Texture of the tube: *Smooth, opaque.*
- Teeth: *None.*
- Colour: *Cream/white*

Frequency on Panels

Common

Less common

Rare

Spirorbinae

M.ID 11

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): /
- Coiling direction: *longitudinal*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *Thick median longitudinal keel, peristomes.*
- Texture of the tube: *Regular alveoli on the sides.*
- Teeth: *1 to 3.*
- Colour: *White*

Serpulinae

M.ID 8

Thick and spiky "tube" in the middle with median keels

One to three tooth

Regular alveoli along the body on both side

Y.D.20

Frequency on Panels

Common

Less common

Rare

B.1.32

B.D.3

S.C.13

S.1.32

W.D.19

W.C.14

B.1.18

Y.2.10-11

S.D.25

W.2.20

W.C.41

B.C.16

B.2.7

W.C.22

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): /
- Coiling direction: *longitudinal*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *4 longitudinal keels (2 laterals and 2 medians).*
- Texture of the tube: "*Fluffy*" on the *extremities, rough.*
- Teeth: *4.*
- Colour: *Pinkish, white*

Frequency on Panels

Common **Less common** Rare

Serpulinae

M.ID 9

External tube morphology:

- Diameter of the tube whorl (mm): /
- Coiling direction: *longitudinal*
- Shell shape: *Planispiral*
- External ornaments: *3 longitudinal keels (2 laterals).*
- Texture of the tube: "*Fluffy*" on the *extremities.*
- Teeth: 3.
- Colour: *White*

Serpulinae

M.ID 10

3 longitudinal ridges Fluffy on the body's extremities 3 teeth

Frequency on Panels		
Common	Less common	Rare

W.C.42

W.1.23

W.D.25

W.2.52

B.1.50

W.C.39